

How important do you see that diversity and inclusion issues are approached in software engineering TEACHING

Scale 0 (not important at all) to 10 (Really important)

Vastaajien määrä: 30

Minimiarvo	Maksimiarvo	Keskiarvo	Mediaani	Summa	Keskihajonta
3.0	10.0	7.6	8.0	228.0	2.1

How important do you see that diversity and inclusion issues are raised up in your own software engineering faculty/team/school.

Scale 0 (not important at all) to 10 (Really important)

Vastaajien määrä: 30

Minimiarvo	Maksimiarvo	Keskiarvo	Mediaani	Summa	Keskihajonta
3.0	10.0	7.5	8.0	226.0	2.3

How satisfied you are on how diversity and inclusion issues are approached in your software engineering faculty/team/school.

Scale 0 (not happy at all) to 10 (Really happy)

Vastaajien määrä: 30

Minimiarvo	Maksimiarvo	Keskiarvo	Mediaani	Summa	Keskihajonta
2.0	10.0	6.3	6.5	190.0	2.2

Teaching experience in years

Vastaajien määrä: 30

	n	Prosentti
<5	5	16.7%
5-10	10	33.3%
11-20	11	36.7%
20+	4	13.3%